

Monte Carlo modeling of the TAPIRO facility with Serpent

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ABSTRACT

The TAPIRO facility can be a valuable asset for the experimental assessment of the performance of different neutron shielding materials. In this respect, a Serpent model of TAPIRO has been developed, exploiting information available in the public literature. Serpent simulations allowed characterizing TAPIRO from the neutronic point of view and identifying interesting features of the facility, like its almost fission spectrum and its extremely low mean neutron generation time. The calculations are performed using the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library, which proved to be the one providing the results nearest to criticality for the current model. In particular, a comparison with other libraries (i.e., JEFF-3.3 and ENDF/B-VII.1) showed that important discrepancies between copper cross sections are present in the three libraries. Physical quantities like material compositions, components size, position of control rods and temperatures are taken into account too, with the aim of assessing the main sources of uncertainties in the model. A comparison with a TAPIRO model independently developed with OpenMC has shown that the two codes provide consistent results.

Keywords: TAPIRO, Monte Carlo, Nuclear Data Libraries, Modeling Uncertainties

1. INTRODUCTION

Neutron activation is one of the main sources of concern in the R&D of lead-cooled fast reactors. This is mainly due to the behavior of lead, which is a very effective material at diffusing neutrons rather than absorbing them. This aspect, if combined with the small size of the reactor, creates difficult conditions for radiation shielding, as the limited space requires innovative solutions to decrease the neutron flux impacting on ex-core structures. Lowering the neutron flux through shielding limits irradiation damage to the structures and limits activation, which is beneficial in terms of both maintenance activities and future decommissioning.

The TAPIRO reactor [1] is a fast spectrum research facility located in ENEA – Casaccia. It is considered a valuable asset, as it is one of the few research reactors with a fast spectrum in Europe that could, under certain circumstances, mimic the irradiation conditions of Generation IV fast reactors [2], and, in particular, of LFR systems, thanks to the similarities between LFR's and TAPIRO's neutron spectra. For this reason, it could be used to test shielding components and assess their effectiveness in attenuating the neutron flux. Moreover, TAPIRO can also be used for the training of reactor operators. This is a particularly important aspect, also in view of the potential installation of future nuclear facilities in Italy.

This paper is focused on the modeling of TAPIRO with Serpent [3]. Serpent has been chosen thanks to its perturbation capabilities [4], that could be used for optimization studies of shielding materials too

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[5]. This optimization procedure is based on the Generalized Perturbation Theory [6], widely adopted in nuclear reactor physics. The quality assessment of the model is performed too, varying some parameters of the model, with the aim of assessing the impact of their uncertainty on the results of the Monte Carlo simulations.

Section 2 briefly describes the TAPIRO reactor and presents the results of the neutronic characterization of the facility using a simplified Serpent model of TAPIRO (Section 2.1), with a particular focus on the effect of copper cross sections and on the flux in the experimental channels of TAPIRO. Then, the impact of uncertainty in other quantities like materials compositions, components size and positions of the control rods is assessed too in Section 2.2. Finally, a comparison between the results obtained with the TAPIRO Serpent model and an OpenMC 0.15.1 [7] model independently developed in *newcleo* is shown in Section 2.3. The availability of an accurate but simple TAPIRO Serpent model is particularly important, since it will allow to faithfully reproduce the real behavior of TAPIRO, without the need of inserting all the geometry details in the model, thus reducing the computational burden.

2. THE TAPIRO REACTOR

Lead Fast Reactors requires the systematic deployment of experimental campaigns to support the R&D of these systems. In this sense, the fast neutrons source TAPIRO (Taratura Pila Rapida Potenza ZerO), in operation since 1971 at Casaccia research center, could play a pivotal role. TAPIRO [1] is equipped with an extremely compact core, with highly enriched uranium metal, enclosed in an AISI 316 L cladding and surrounded by a copper reflector. This feature leads to an almost pure fission spectrum in the core center, accessible through part of the experimental channels. The small core, cooled by helium gas, is cylindrical and is composed of seven disks. The five lower disks can move vertically for emergency shutdown or to allow the installation of irradiation samples into the fuel cavity. The fission spectrum characterizing the core of TAPIRO translates in a fast spectrum in the copper reflector, where the experimental channels can be exploited to place samples of shielding materials and test them in a neutronic environment characteristic of LFR systems. The copper reflector is characterized by an internal region and an external one, separated by a layer of AISI 304 steel. AISI 304 is also used to separate the external reflector and the borated concrete shield surrounding the neutron source. The coatings of all the channels are made of AISI 304 too. The reflector contains the control rod system that can be vertically inserted to increase the reactivity of the facility. Finally, outside the copper reflector and inside the biological shielding, there is the thermal column. This component is a large cavity characterized by a more thermalised spectrum. Thanks to its size, it can be employed to test larger samples.

Figure 1. *x-y* view of the TAPIRO Serpent model, with the location of the experimental channels and of the thermal column. Fuel is red, copper is ochre and the borated concrete is purple. The black circles below the core are the control rods.

A Serpent model of TAPIRO has been developed in this work and it is shown in Figure 1, with the

indication of the location of the different experimental channels.

This model is a simplified version of the real TAPIRO reactor. In fact, the fuel in TAPIRO is made of several stacked disks with different fuel compositions, while here the same composition is used in the whole fuel. Then, there are additional vertical channels passing through the copper reflector, which have not been modeled here for lack of information. Also, the systems for the movement of the control rods and of the movable core are not present in the model for the same reasons. In the following section, the results of the neutronic characterization of TAPIRO with this simplified model will be presented, with the identification of the main sources of uncertainties in the model and in the nuclear data. +

2.1. Neutronic characterization

A reference critical configuration has been defined with the following criteria:

- nuclear data library: ENDF/B-VIII.0 [8]
- copper density: 99% natural Cu;
- Control Rods position: Safety Rods 1 and 2 87% inserted, Shim Rods 1 and 2 33% inserted, Regulation Rod 27% inserted;
- Steel: AISI 316 L in the fuel cladding and AISI 304 in the gap between the internal and external reflector, between the external reflector and the shielding and in the coating of the experimental channels;
- core temperature: 430 K;
- fuel composition: ratio between ^{238}U and ^{234}U concentration equal to 225.

These parameters have been slightly perturbed in different Serpent simulations to determine their impact on the integral parameters of TAPIRO. The copper density has been reduced to mimic the presence of void regions which are present in TAPIRO but that have not been modelled in Serpent.

As a starting point, the values of important integral parameters like the multiplication factor k_{eff} , the effective delayed neutron fraction β_{eff} and the effective mean neutron generation time Λ_{eff} have been computed with different nuclear data libraries (NDL), using the reference configuration. The results in Table I show that the k_{eff} obtained with ENDF/B-VIII.0 is the nearest one to the criticality. Also the values of Λ_{eff} are quite different according to the employed NDL, while β_{eff} is almost independent of the NDL in this case. This behavior can be explained considering the high enrichment of the TAPIRO core. Thus, since the cross sections of ^{235}U in the different NDL are extremely similar, also the values of β_{eff} are almost the same. On the other hand, the copper reflector has a non-negligible impact on k_{eff} and Λ_{eff} . In particular, the cross sections of copper are quite different between the three NDL. Using a modified version of ENDF/B-VII.1 [9] and of JEFF-3.3 [10] with nuclear data of copper coming from the ENDF/B-VIII.0 (chosen because it provides the result nearest to criticality), the k_{eff} and Λ_{eff} of TAPIRO obtained with the three libraries approach the same result (Table II). In particular, results in Table II have been obtained substituting at first only ^{63}Cu and the second time both ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu . The β_{eff} value is characteristic of U-fuelled systems, while the extremely small Λ_{eff} is a consequence of the fast spectrum of TAPIRO.

	k_{eff} (-)	Λ_{eff} (ns)	β_{eff} (pcm)
ENDF/B-VIII.0	0.99967 ± 21 pcm	45.80 ± 0.07	665 ± 1
ENDF/B-VII.1	1.00539 ± 20 pcm	44.26 ± 0.06	676 ± 1
JEFF-3.3	1.00461 ± 20 pcm	43.40 ± 0.06	665 ± 1

Table I. Integral parameters of TAPIRO with different nuclear data libraries, with statistical (1σ) uncertainties.

Considering that TAPIRO is a critical facility and that ENDF/B-VIII.0 provides results nearer to criticality with the current model, this library has been employed for the following analysis. At first, the

	k_{eff}	Λ_{eff} (ns)		k_{eff}	Λ_{eff} (ns)
JEFF-3.3	1.00461	43.4	ENDF/B-VII.1	1.00539	44.3
^{63}Cu	0.99759	45.2	^{63}Cu	0.99827	45.3
^{65}Cu	0.99802	45.4	^{65}Cu	1.00019	45.3
ENDF/B-VIII.0	0.99967	45.8	ENDF/B-VIII.0	0.99967	45.8

Table II. Effect of the incremental update of the nuclear data of JEFF-3.3 and ENDF/B-VII.1 with the nuclear data of ENDF/B-VIII.0 on the k_{eff} and Λ_{eff} .

neutron flux in the diametral channel has been computed using a detector defined on a cartesian mesh and discriminating between a fast flux ($E > 0.1$ MeV), an intermediate flux ($500 \text{ eV} < E < 0.1$ MeV), an epithermal flux ($0.025 \text{ eV} < E < 500 \text{ eV}$) and a thermal flux ($E < 0.025 \text{ eV}$). In Figure 2, it can be noticed that at a radial distance of 30 cm from the core center, the intermediate flux becomes higher due to the moderating effect of copper. Finally, the fast flux becomes again the highest in the biological shielding at 75 cm, due to radiative capture of borated concrete, which is much more important for slower neutrons. The neutron flux values for negative and positive positions in the diametral channel are an indication of the symmetry of TAPIRO from the neutronic point of view.

Figure 2. Neutron flux in the diametral channel of TAPIRO

2.2. Parametric analysis

In this section, a parametric analysis on TAPIRO is presented, showing which is the impact of small variations in some input parameters of the model on the integral parameters computed by Serpent. The different test cases are shown in Table III. Here, the aim is to understand which of the quantities that can not be found or that are not uniquely provided in the literature have the largest impact on the final results, requiring a more detailed analysis in order to have a more accurate TAPIRO model. Moreover, this analysis will also provide useful insights about the physics of TAPIRO.

Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5
CRs position	Core volume	Cu density	Fuel temperature	U composition

Table III. Description of quantities modified in each case study.

At first, the position of the two Safety Rods have been moved 2 cm out of the core (i.e., 73% insertion) in order to have a rough estimation of the change of reactivity per cm of CR extraction. It can be expected

that the information obtained moving only one type of CR can be representative of the other rods too, due to the symmetry of TAPIRO. The k_{eff} obtained with the new configuration is lower, in line with the fact that the copper control rods in TAPIRO are extracted with the aim of decreasing the reactivity of the reactor. The kinetic parameters are weakly affected by this modification, as shown in Table IV, where the relative difference (RD) with respect to the reference case is computed too. The value of β_{eff} is 9 pcm higher than the reference one probably because in this configuration the neutron spectrum is faster, because there are less reflections in the copper due to the partial extraction of the control rods. This increases the number of fissions occurring in ^{238}U which, having a delayed neutron multiplicity larger than ^{235}U , slightly increases β_{eff} .

k_{eff} (-)	Λ_{eff} (ns)	β_{eff} (pcm)	$RD_{k_{\text{eff}}}$ (pcm)	$RD_{\Lambda_{\text{eff}}}$ (%)	$RD_{\beta_{\text{eff}}}$ (%)
0.98294 ± 20 pcm	45.61 ± 0.06	674 ± 1	-138	-0.4	1.3

Table IV. Integral parameters of TAPIRO computed in Case 1 (different CR position), with statistical (1σ) uncertainties. RD is the relative difference with respect to the reference case.

Another quantity that is not uniquely provided in the literature is the volume of the core. Considering that this is the most important component of TAPIRO, it is reasonable to expect that little variations in its size can lead to non-negligible differences in the integral parameters. Thus, a new larger core has been modeled, providing the results shown in table Table V. As expected, k_{eff} is significantly increased, while β_{eff} is almost the same (the fuel composition has not been changed), as well as Λ_{eff} (which strongly depends on the isotopic composition and density of the copper reflector, which have not been modified in this test case). However, Λ_{eff} is slightly smaller because having a larger core increases the probability of having fissions, reducing the mean generation time.

k_{eff} (-)	Λ_{eff} (ns)	β_{eff} (pcm)	$RD_{k_{\text{eff}}}$ (pcm)	$RD_{\Lambda_{\text{eff}}}$ (%)	$RD_{\beta_{\text{eff}}}$ (%)
1.00589 ± 21 pcm	45.06 ± 0.06	661 ± 1	622	-1.6	-0.6

Table V. Integral parameters of TAPIRO computed in Case 2 (larger core), with statistical (1σ) uncertainties. RD is the relative difference with respect to the reference case.

Then, also the copper density in the reflector has been changed, passing from a density equal to 99% of the natural density of Cu to a 100 % density. The use of a reduced density for the copper reflector of TAPIRO, can be motivated with the aim of taking into account the presence of some void regions in the reflector that are not defined in the Serpent model [11]. Also in this case, the effect on k_{eff} is non-negligible (Table VI), with an increase caused by the higher density of copper which translates in a larger amount of neutrons reflected into the core.

k_{eff} (-)	Λ_{eff} (ns)	β_{eff} (pcm)	$RD_{k_{\text{eff}}}$ (pcm)	$RD_{\Lambda_{\text{eff}}}$ (%)	$RD_{\beta_{\text{eff}}}$ (%)
1.00211 ± 21 pcm	45.71 ± 0.06	674 ± 1	244	-0.1	1.5

Table VI. Integral parameters of TAPIRO computed in Case 3 (denser Cu), with statistical (1σ) uncertainties. RD is the relative difference with respect to the reference case.

An average temperature of 430K in the fuel has been assumed in the reference configuration. However, since the temperature at the center of the core is higher, it is reasonable to perform a new simulation with a higher average fuel temperature (523K), corresponding to the one at the center of the fuel, to assess the impact of the Doppler effect. Here, the thermal expansions have not been accounted, to focus

on the Doppler effect only. However the change of size corresponding to an increase of temperature ~ 100 K is comparable to the one considered in Table V. Table VII shows that, in this case, the differences due to the Doppler effect are small, suggesting that higher tolerance on the evaluation of the fuel temperature can be accepted. Here, higher temperature variations have not been taken into account, since significative temperature excursion for the fuel temperature of TAPIRO are not expected. The corresponding Doppler coefficient (i.e., $\partial\rho/\partial T$) is ~ 0.5 pcm/K, which is slightly positive. However, this result could be affected by the non-negligible statistical uncertainty of k_{eff} .

k_{eff} (-)	Λ_{eff} (ns)	β_{eff} (pcm)	$RD_{k_{\text{eff}}}$ (pcm)	$RD_{\Lambda_{\text{eff}}}$ (%)	$RD_{\beta_{\text{eff}}}$ (%)
1.00006 ± 22 pcm	46.01 ± 0.07	679 ± 1	39	0.5	2.2

Table VII. Integral parameters of TAPIRO computed in Case 4 (higher fuel temperature), with statistical (1σ) uncertainties. RD is the relative difference with respect to the reference case.

Then, there are not specific indications about the composition of fuel. Thus, we can assume that the quantity of ^{234}U can be higher (ratio between ^{238}U and ^{234}U concentration equal to 13) to see which is the impact of this variation of the fuel composition. As can be seen in Table VIII, this variation leads to an increase of the k_{eff} , mainly due to the fact that the fission cross section of ^{234}U is higher than the one of ^{238}U .

k_{eff} (-)	Λ_{eff} (ns)	β_{eff} (pcm)	$RD_{k_{\text{eff}}}$ (pcm)	$RD_{\Lambda_{\text{eff}}}$ (%)	$RD_{\beta_{\text{eff}}}$ (%)
1.00188 ± 22 pcm	45.70 ± 0.07	664 ± 1	221	-0.2	-0.07

Table VIII. Integral parameters of TAPIRO computed in Case 5 (different fuel composition), with statistical (1σ) uncertainties. RD is the relative difference with respect to the reference case.

Conversely, the type of steel employed in the model plays a negligible role, mainly due to its extremely small volume. For this reason, the results obtained considering different types of steel are not presented here.

2.3. Comparison between Serpent and OpenMC models

Finally, a code to code comparison between the Serpent reference model presented in this work and an OpenMC model independently developed in *newcleo* has been performed, to guarantee that both could be used to accurately characterize the TAPIRO facility. In the OpenMC model, the experimental channels and the control rods are not present, so the density of the copper has been artificially decreased to take into account the presence of void regions in the Serpent model. The density reduction due to the absence of the control rods is justified by the fact that in Serpent there are some void regions when the control rods are not completely inserted, while, in the case of OpenMC, these regions are made of copper.

The comparison, made using the ENDF/B-VIII.0 library, is focused on the value of k_{eff} obtained with the two codes and on the neutron spectra in the core, in the reflector and in the shielding, sampled over a 500 lethargy-uniform groups energy grid. The k_{eff} computed with OpenMC is equal to 0.99973 ± 2 pcm, with a discrepancy of 6 pcm with respect to Serpent. Finally, the comparison of the neutron fluxes integrated over the three main components of TAPIRO is shown in Figure 3, together with the relative difference (RD) between the two codes. It can be seen that a good agreement between the spectra in the fuel and in the concrete shield is reached, in particular in regions where the flux is higher. Instead, in the case of the copper reflector, the discrepancy is non-negligible in the energy range between 10^{-5} and 10^{-2} MeV (where OpenMC underestimates the flux), probably due to the fact that the OpenMC model does

Figure 3. Comparison of the neutron spectra computed with Serpent and OpenMC.

not include the channels and the control rods and, thus, contains a larger amount of copper. However, it is reasonable to state that both the models are able to reproduce the neutronic environment in TAPIRO and also that a less detailed model like the OpenMC one can be used for preliminary analyses.

This analysis indicates that the reference Serpent model developed in this work is quite accurate, providing the k_{eff} nearest to criticality among the different cases tested here, and that the impact of small parameters changes on k_{eff} is non-negligible. On the other hand, the kinetic parameters are weakly affected by changes in the model. This also means that, for the calibration of the TAPIRO model, it would be better to use experimental values of k_{eff} instead of kinetic parameters.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The Monte Carlo calculations with the simplified TAPIRO Serpent model developed in this work using the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library provided values of k_{eff} , β_{eff} and Λ_{eff} consistent with the neutronic features of TAPIRO, pointing towards the good quality of the model. Non-negligible discrepancies between copper cross sections of ENDF/B-VIII.0, JEFF-3.3 and ENDF/B-VII.1 were shown, which explain the major parts of discrepancies in k_{eff} between the different libraries. Then, several quantities like the position of the control rods, the size of the core, the density of the copper, the composition and the temperature of the fuel were changed to assess their impact on the three integral parameters of TAPIRO and to understand which quantities have to be treated with particular attention in the preparation of the model. This analysis showed that the two kinetic parameters are almost independent of geometry and material uncertainties in the model, while k_{eff} is particularly sensitive to the volume of the fuel, the copper density, the fuel composition and the position of the control rods. The effect of the

fuel temperature is almost null. Then, thanks to the comparison between the Serpent model and an OpenMC one independently developed, it was shown that the effect of neglecting the modeling of the experimental channels and the control rods is non-negligible. In the future, the OpenMC model will be further adjusted to increase the agreement with the Serpent one and both the models will be calibrated against experimental values of TAPIRO. After having assessed the impact of the Serpent model uncertainties and its agreement with OpenMC, this model could be used for more detailed investigations in TAPIRO, like the characterization of neutron shielding samples to be experimentally tested in the facility, selected thanks to the use of GPT capabilities of Serpent.

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